

TEACHING ETHICAL REASONING TO ENGINEERING STUDENTS

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Abstract

Engineering ethics is an important component of engineering education. Yet the topic is seldom covered in mainstream engineering education, partly due to the wide-ranging nature of ethical issues. Especially of concern is the rapid advancement of technology, in particular in the advent of Internet of Things, while bringing about greater convenience and availability of information, also threatens personal and data privacy. This paper presents an initial effort by a team of lecturers from the Diploma in Chemical Engineering to teach ethical reasoning to its students. While not directly related to addressing the ethical issues related to technologies per se, we believe this is an important first step towards greater coverage of engineering ethics in education. Due to an already packed curriculum, the topic is introduced as part of the study of chemical process plant safety, a 60-hour core module in Year 3 titled *Plant Safety and Loss Prevention*. The paper starts with a brief introduction to engineering ethics, and shares various ways – based on a survey of the literature – how engineering ethics can be integrated into the curriculum. Then, after a brief introduction to the module, the paper presents the work done by the team, which involved the use of the DVD *Incident at Morales*, a professionally-produced teaching aid, as an assessable assignment. The objectives are to introduce our students to potential ethical issues related to engineering work, heighten their awareness in recognizing them, and how they can reason through possible resolutions using the engineering profession's code of practice. Essentially the work done is via facilitated classroom discussion, where scenes from the DVD are identified as posing potential ethical issues, and how these can be addressed, with students putting themselves in the shoes of the main actors. Students are assessed through a presentation in MP4 format. The paper then shares the finding of students' learning experience via surveys, which include questions that are part of the DVD package, as well as additional questions posed by the teaching team. The paper concludes with some ideas to further improve the teaching of engineering ethics.

Keywords: *CDIO, Chemical Engineering, Ethical Reasoning, Code of Ethics*

Introduction: Importance of Engineering Ethics

Being able to practice in an ethical manner is expected of engineers. Therefore, the teaching of ethics should be an important component of all engineering education. Colby & Sullivan (2008) suggested that training of professionals in all fields can be designated as 3 formative apprenticeships as follows:

Figure 1. Apprenticeship of Professional Training

However, the teaching of ethics in engineering profession as currently practiced is still inadequate (Herkert, 2010; Colby & Sullivan, 2008). The rapid progress in technology development, in particular Internet of Things, had raised concerns (Waddell, 2017). For example, Stahl et al (2017) probed the social and ethical implications of research and innovations in emerging technologies such as artificial intelligence, cloud computing and robotics. Wadhwa (2014) went further and noted that technological progress is moving further ahead than the legal and moral frameworks needed to manage it. From a different perspective, several authors had also argued that teaching of ethics is important for the development of professional identity in one's chosen field (e.g. Stappenbelt, 2012; Loui, 2005).

Sternberg (2012) argued that ethical reasoning can be taught, and best with the case study approach. Ethical reason is distinct from ethics – the former is how to think about issues of right or wrong, whereas the latter comprises a set of principles for what constitute right and wrong behaviour (Sternberg, 2012). Also, as noted by

Adamson (2017), while ethical behaviour is about doing the right thing, it doesn't follow that the right thing is intuitively obvious. Just as engineers and technologists learn to assess risks in their work, they need to learn how to identify ethically challenging circumstances.

Integrate Engineering Ethics into Curriculum

There is clearly an increasing need for educational institutions to teach ethics to better prepare students for today's workplace (Frisque et. al, 2004). However, there is no one consistent, widely agreed-upon method of teaching ethics to undergraduates, and literature indicates disagreement about approaches to teaching ethical practice (Baker, et al, 2012). Various approaches had been suggested to integrate engineering ethics into a curriculum. Some of these are 'standalone' approaches (e.g. Hornsby, 2007), where a separate module is introduced, and the teaching may not be directly related to any core modules and often taught by faculty not belonging to the engineering profession. Others tend to link teaching of engineering ethics with the execution of capstone projects (e.g. Jiménez, et al, 2006; Leone & Isaacs, 2001). Our approach in the Diploma in Chemical Engineering (DCHE) is based on what Davis & Riley (2008) termed "insertion", which involved the inclusion of ethics instruction into technical modules resulting in a dozen or so "ethics mini-lessons". A micro-insertion is one that is small-scale, each lasting only a few minutes. The work described here is one that is significantly longer, as presented next. In this case, we use the video *Incident at Morales* and integrate it into the module *Plant Safety and Loss Prevention*.

The video is a product of the combined efforts of a team with representation from several universities and individuals with experience in various engineering disciplines and philosophy. It was developed by The National Institute for Engineering Ethics (NIEE), Murdough Centre for Engineering Professionalism, Texas Tech University, with a grant from the National Science Foundation.

This video is chosen because it provides the suitable context for the chemical engineering discipline. It involves a variety of ethical issues faced by a company that wants to quickly build a chemical plant in order to develop a new chemical product to gain a competitive edge over the competition. Potential technical and ethical issues arise from choices of designs, including valves, piping, chemicals, etc. The process involves high temperatures and pressures and requires the use of chemicals that need special handling. The plant is designed to be automated and controlled using computer software. Because of cost factors, the company decides to construct their plant in Mexico and uses cheaper parts and components (Smith & Nichols, 2004). Various problems of different nature (technical, environmental, financial, and safety) arisen that involve ethical issues. The movie emphasized 3 aspects:

- Ethical considerations are an integral part of making engineering decisions.

- Although legal requirements may vary among states and nations, ethical obligations do not stop at state or national borders.
- Wherever engineer practice, they should strive to protect the health, safety, and welfare of the public.

Description of Work Done

Plant Safety and Loss Prevention is a core module taught to all 120 DCHE students in Year 3. It is non-examinable, i.e. it is 100% based on in-course assessment, as shown in Table 1.

Table 1. Module Assessment Plan

Code	Description	Type	Percentage
CA1	Assignment: HAZOP Report	Group	20
MST	Mid-Semester Test	Individual	20
CA2	Case Study: Singapore Standards	Group	15
	Assignment: <i>Incident at Morales</i>	Group	15
EST	End-of-Semester Test	Individual	30

The module was taught in semester 1, with 4 hours contact time per week, over 2 terms for a total of 15 weeks, not including the 3-week term break in-between. The lesson on teaching ethical reasoning was conducted over Weeks 16 and 17 (total 8 hours) as follows. Students are first reminded (i.e. to activate their prior knowledge) of their Year 1 study in the module *Introduction to Chemical Engineering* where the Bhopal Gas Disaster and ethical issues were first introduced. The class then goes on with more in-depth discussion such as identifying key stakeholders and their perspectives. This sets the stage for exploring potential ethical issues and ethical reasoning using the *Incident at Morales* video.

The video is about 35 minutes long. It was played in class and paused at appropriate intervals whereby he lecturer then initiated classroom discussion to clarify scenes in the video, and to engage students in identifying potential ethical issues. Collectively, the class (comprising 20-24 students, working in groups of 4-5 students per group) record the discussions into Google Doc (see Table 2). At this point, any group can help with the recording. The purpose is to capture the key points of the discussion. Later, students were given time to watch the video again to better understand the entire storyline. Students were then informed that each group is to select one ethical issue of technical nature and another ethical issue of non-technical nature for their assignment; and no groups can work on the same issues. Each group recorded its choice with an "X" in Table 2 for all to see. Selection is on a first-come-first serve basis.

Students are also briefed on the assessment requirement of the assignment, which is worth 15% of the overall assessment (see Table 1). It requires students to prepare a presentation in-class or via a video. Specific details of this assessment are shown in Table 3. Lesson then continues with the lecturer facilitating the discussion on ethical reasoning. Students were given up to one week to complete the assignment.

Table 2. Google Doc for Recording Discussion Outcome

		Class:					Group:				
S/N		Brief Description of Issues					A	B	C	D	E
Technical	T1										
	T2										
	T3										
	T4										
	T5										
	T6										
Non-technical	N1										
	N2										
	N3										
	N4										
	N5										
	N6										

Table 3. Assessment for *Incident at Morales*

Assessment Component (Group)	Percentage
• Analysis of Ethical Issues: 1 Technical, 1 Non-Tech	40
• “If You Were In-Charge”	20
• Creativity / Presentation Skills	20
Assessment Component (Individual)	Percentage
• Class Participation, Completion of Surveys	20

A total of 3 surveys were carried out. The first two surveys use the same set of 5 questions devised by Loui (2006), who used the video to investigate students’ learning of engineering ethics; but adapted them to Singapore’s context for one of the questions. His study showed that the video is an effective approach to teach engineering ethics. One survey was administered before students watch the video, and another survey after they watched the video and classroom discussion. The 5 questions are:

- S1. The first obligation of an engineer is to fulfil an assignment from the employer, or a contract of a client
- S2. When working in a foreign country, a Singaporean engineer should comply with local regulations and should avoid imposing more stringent Singapore standards for safety
- S3. Ethics consideration are an integral part of making engineering decisions
- S4. A code of ethics can provide guidance in making engineering decisions
- S5. Many ethical problems encountered by engineers have technical solutions

For each question, students are to indicate on a Likert Scale their responses: from 1 for “Strongly Disagree” to 5 for “Strongly Agree”. The third survey is prepared by the author to learn about the students’ learning experience in engineering ethics based on an active learning approach used in classroom. There are 10 question with a Likert Scale ranging from 1 “Strong Disagree” to 5 “Strongly Agree”:

- Q1. I find that the lessons from “*Incident at Morales*” had provided me with new understanding of the

role and responsibilities (i.e. that of ethics) of a chemical engineer.

- Q2. I have developed greater awareness of potential ethical issues that may arise from the conduct of a chemical engineer in the workplace.
- Q3. I believe that having a good understanding of ethical principles is important for the professional identity of a chemical engineer.
- Q4. I find the approach used in class (use of probing questions, reminder of selected scenes, or words spoken) useful in helping me identifying potential ethical issues in “*Incident at Morales*”.
- Q5. I enjoy participating in my group discussion analyzing ethical issues in “*Incident at Morales*”.
- Q6. I have learnt to analyze a technical issue for its potential ethical implications.
- Q7. I have learnt where to obtain more resources and some tools needed to help me resolve an ethical dilemma that I may face.
- Q8. I find that including learning of ethics in the chemical engineering curriculum is beneficial to me.
- Q9. I find that working collaboratively in Google Doc is a useful way to identify as many ethical issues as possible in “*Incident at Morales*”.
- Q10. Overall, I benefitted from the lessons in analyzing ethical issues covered in “*Incident at Morales*”.

Results and Discussions

We will first discuss the results from the 5-question Pre- and Post-video surveys, shown in Figures 1 to 5 as obtained from 2 cohorts of students in 2 semesters. The results in Figure 1 is encouraging, as it showed that there is an increased awareness that the obligation of an engineer went beyond that of employers or clients. There is a shift in the numbers of responses that indicated “Agree” or “Strongly agree” towards “Strongly disagree”. This showed that the broad intended learning outcome had been achieved, i.e. the commitment that an engineer should have is towards health society and welfare of the public.

Likewise, Figures 3 to 5 represented changes in students perceptions that were not unexpected. Students recognized that ethical considerations is part of engineering decision-making; and felt that having a code of ethics is useful. In Figure 3 there is a significant increase in responses towards “Strongly agree” that ethics consideration are an integral part of engineering decision-making, confirming the shift noted in Figure 1. There is minimal change seen in Figure 4: we take it that all along students opined that a code of ethics is useful in guiding their decision-making. As for Figure 5, it showed a shift in students’ belief that many ethical problems can have engineering solutions.

An interesting situation came from Figure 2, which suggests that when in a foreign country, an engineer should comply with local regulations and should avoid imposing more-stringent Singapore standards for safety. Here there is negligible change overall, due to ‘cancellation’ effect as shown in Table 4.

Figure 1. Response to Pre- and Post-Video Survey S1.

Figure 5. Response to Pre- and Post-Video Survey S5.

Figure 2. Response to Pre- and Post-Video Survey S2.

Figure 6. Response to Learning Experience Survey Set 1

Figure 3. Response to Pre- and Post-Video Survey S3.

Figure 7. Response to Learning Experience Survey Set 2

Figure 4. Response to Pre- and Post-Video Survey S4.

Table 4. Results from Figure 2.

Video	% Response				
	S Agree	Agree	Neither	Disagree	S Disagree
Post-	9	32	23	25	11
Pre-	14	26	30	25	4
Change	-5	+6	-7	0	+7

The pattern of the shift indicates that there seem to be confusion among students on which country takes precedence on ethical matters – his/her home country or the country he/she is working in. This means that we

should spend a bit more time during the lesson debrief to address the issue. Timing-wise this can be challenging because the post-survey can only be done after students watched the video and class discussions completed. At this point students tend to be more interested in continuing with the assignment than completing this post-video survey, even if we stop conducting the third survey.

Next, we look at the students' learning experiences in the topic by examining the results from the third survey. Responses to Questions 1, 2 and 3 as captured in Figure 6 showed that students can readily identify with the need for chemical engineers to conduct themselves in an ethical manner. Most students also reported that they felt engaged by the approach used in teaching the subject, as shown by responses to Questions 4 and 5 in Figure 6. This is again reaffirmed by the students in their response to Question 9 in Figure 7, on the use of Google Doc. Based on the authors' experience, students often came up with more numbers of ethical issues (both of technical and non-technical nature) than required. As mentioned in earlier paragraph, the requirement is that no group should work on the same issues; i.e. if there are 5 groups, then there should be 5 different technical and 5 different non-technical ethical issues identified. However, in all instances, the students usually came up with 6 or 7 different issues for each category.

On their skills development, students generally reported that they had improved in the ability to analyse a potential ethical issue (Question 6), and be more resourceful when seeking more information (Question 7). Overall, they believed that learning about ethics is a useful endeavour (Questions 8 and 10).

Due to time constraint, we are not able to allocate as much time needed for classroom discussion using the approach suggested in the training guide. Another challenge faced is the need to invest some time to explain some of the scenes, for example, how a multi-national corporation operates (for example as in the *Incident at Morales* case, which involve a parent company in France, with the subsidiary in the U.S., building a new plant in Mexico), or the terminologies used in the dialogues among the actors due to the students's lack of real-world working experience.

An interesting finding though, was the preference shown by students for sharing their work, which contributed to 15% of total module assessment. This was in fact a chance encounter: for Academic Year 2017, due to clashing of class schedule with national public holiday, students were given options to either send in a video submission of Week 17, or do a classroom presentation to the lecturer on Week 18. The latter had been the traditional approach of assessment used in previous years. All except one group opted for the video presentation. As can be seen from Table 3, use of creativity in presenting the materials is one of the assessment criteria.

As things turned out, students handed in more interesting work based on their video submissions. There were much creativity displayed in presenting the assignment, in terms of analysis of ethical issues, and the segment on "If You Were In-Charge" (Table 3) using a wide range of media such as PowToon, VideoScribe, or

they simply just film themselves in role play. For the author, this outcome is much more desirable than sitting in class going through one PowerPoint presentation after another.

Ideas for Future Work

The survey results are very encouraging to the team, which prompted us to think of ways to build on what we had done thus far, to further deepen the students' engagement in learning about engineering ethics. We come up some ideas for future work:

- (a) We can consider consolidating the separate cases of ethical issues currently integrated in various core chemical modules under a common theme, such as using a spiral curriculum (Whysong, et al, 2007). An opportunity to do so now available, as the course is now undergoing a revamp to align itself with the requirement of a national-level initiative (Cheah & Yang, 2018).
- (b) Introduce a systematic process for ethical reasoning, to help students analyse ethical issues. An example is the Sternberg's 8-step process (Sternberg, 2012):
 1. Recognize that there is an event to which to react
 2. Define the event as having an ethical dimension
 3. Decide that the ethical dimension is significant.
 4. Take personal responsibility for generating an ethical solution to the problem.
 5. Figure out what abstract ethical rule(s) might apply to the problem.
 6. Decide how these abstract ethical rules actually apply to the problem so as to suggest a concrete solution.
 7. Prepare to counteract contextual forces that might lead one not to act in an ethical manner.
 8. Act
- (c) The logical next step after students had acquired the ethical reasoning skills is for us to assess how well they are able to use it in various situations. In this case, we can refer to the works of Self & Ellison (1998) who investigated the use of Defining Issues Test (DIT), which is based on cognitive moral development theory, as the instrument of assessment of moral reasoning skills. They found that the teaching of ethics in engineering can be rigorously measured, tested and analysed and can have a significant positive influence on the moral reasoning skills of the students.

Strategy (a) can and should rightfully be implemented within the DCHE curriculum itself, as this can best provide the right context of learning about ethical issues in chemical engineering setting. This approach can also support a longitudinal study to track students' skills in handling ethical issues over the duration of their study. Students can be taught to recognize potential ethical issues early in their study, right in Year 1. They can then learn the systematic way to deal with such issues via Strategy (b) for example in Year 2. Evaluation of their competency in ethical reasoning can be carried out in Year 3 using Strategy (c).

The challenge here is for the team to figure out how best to do this in a curriculum that is already packed. Where can Strategies (b) and (c) best incorporated is not immediately clear at this point. The Year 2 curriculum is particularly congested. An alternative may be to explore this as an elective module offered in Year 3, combining both Strategies (b) and (c). The on-going revamp effort may help to inspire some new creative ways.

Conclusions

This paper shared the work done to develop in students skills in ethical reasoning. From the results obtained, we can conclude that students had gained greater awareness of potential ethical issues in engineering, but still need practices to hone the skills required. We had acquired new understanding from this effort, and come up with new ideas of improving the teaching. Although we are still far away from addressing the concerns of technology as mentioned in the beginning of the paper, the author believed the effort made thus far is one that is pointing in the right direction.

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